

Synthesis of some 2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones and 4-Arylidine-3-phenyl-5-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)pyrazoles

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Certain chloro-substituted-2-arylacrylophenones (2) have been prepared by the interaction of 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)-3-phenylpropan-1,3-dione (1) and aromatic aldehydes. These on reaction with hydrazine gave pyrazoles (3).

ACRYLOPHENONES are known for their biological activities¹. Pyrazoles have also been found to possess considerable pharmacological activities². Recently, the synthesis of substituted-2-benzoyl-acrylophenones and 4-arylidine-3,5-diarylpyrazoles have been reported from this laboratory³. In view of known biological activity enhancing effect of halogen atoms, it was proposed to prepare some acrylophenones and pyrazoles in which one of the benzenoid rings invariably contained a chlorine atom. The present communication describes the synthesis of some 2'-hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones (2) and 4-arylidine-3-phenyl-5-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)pyrazoles (3).

The interaction of 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)-3-phenylpropan-1,3-dione (1) and benzaldehyde in presence of piperidine in boiling ethanol afforded a solid (2a), m.p. 67°, which gave dark-red colour with concentrated H₂SO₄ and violet colour with neutral FeCl₃ solution.

A few other 2'-hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-benzoyl-3-aryl acrylophenones (2b-g) were prepared by the extension of this method (Table 1). 4-Arylidine-3-phenyl-5-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)pyrazoles (3a-e) were obtained by refluxing acrylophenones (2a-d, 2g) with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (2 AND 3)*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	Phenyl	67	67
2b	2-Chlorophenyl	156	72
2c	4-Chlorophenyl	151	78
2d	4-Tolyl	75	69
2e	4-Anisyl	79	80
2f	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	76	79
2g	3-Pyridyl	212	56
3a	Phenyl	161	66
3b	2-Chlorophenyl	220	69
3c	4-Chlorophenyl	185	72
3d	4-Tolyl	287	70
3e	3-Pyridyl	230	65

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Experimental

2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-benzoyl-3-phenylacrylophenone (2a): A mixture of 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)-3-phenylpropan-1,3-dione (1; 2 g), benzaldehyde (0.6 g), piperidine (a few drops) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (67%), m.p. 67° (Found: C, 71.9; H, 3.92. Requires: C, 72.8; H, 4.13%); ν_{\max} 3 025 (OH), 1 690 (C=O) and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 5.7 (1H, s, C=CH), 11.8 (1H, s, OH) and 7.00-7.9 (14H, m, ArH). Similarly 2b-g were prepared.

4-Benzylidene-3-phenyl-5-(2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorophenyl)pyrazole (3a): To a solution of 2'-hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-benzoyl-3-phenylacrylophenone (2a; 1 g) in ethanol (15 ml), was added hydrazine hydrate (40%; 4 ml) and refluxed for 1 h. It was then cooled and poured over ice, and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol, (66%), m.p. 161° (Found: C, 72.87; H, 4.1; N, 7.1. Requires: C, 73.43; H, 4.45; N, 7.78%); ν_{\max} 3 060 (OH), 1 580 (C=N) and 1 485 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 10.5 (s, OH) and 6.8-7.7 (14H, m, ArH). The pyrazoles (3b-e) were prepared similarly.

Biological activity: All the compounds were evaluated for their stimulatory and inhibitory activity against groundnut rhizobium. The rhizobium was isolated from the root nodules of groundnut SB-11 (*Arachis hypogae* L.) on yeast extract manitol-agar (YEMA). The stimulatory and inhibitory activities of the compounds were tested by filter paper disc plate method⁴. The compounds were dissolved in ethanol. Discs (4 mm dia) were prepared such that each disc contained 0.02 mg of the compound after evaporation of ethanol under aseptic condition. The discs were then placed on YEMA medium seeded with 3-day old culture of rhizobium. Stimulation or inhibition zones were measured after 6 days. The discs without any compound served as control. The compounds 3b and 3c showed moderate stimulatory activity (+2) while all the acrylophenones (2a-g) were found to be inactive.

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